

1 Editorial

2 **Special Issue “Rain Sensors”**3 **Filippo Giannetti ^{1,*}, Luca Giovanni Lanza ^{2,3}**4 ¹ Department of Information Engineering (DII), University of Pisa, 56122 Pisa, Italy5 ² Department of Civil, Chemical and Environmental Engineering (DICCA), University of Genova, 16145 Ge-
6 nova, Italy7 ³ WMO Measurement Lead Centre “B. Castelli” on Precipitation Intensity, Genoa, Italy8 * Correspondence: filippo.giannetti@unipi.it
910 **1. Introduction**

11 In-situ weather sensors aiming at the measurement of liquid atmospheric precipita-
12 tion (rainfall) experienced limited conceptual innovation in the recent decades, except for
13 the data recording and transmission components. The most relevant advancement in
14 modern rainfall measurement devices remains the transition from catching to non-catch-
15 ing instruments. The former ones are used to measure the integral properties of rainfall
16 (the total amount and intensity of the rainwater collected through a funnel), while recent
17 sensors (most of them contactless) can detect the microphysical features of the rainfall
18 process (e.g., the drop size distribution and fall velocity) or the kinetic energy of each
19 drop. These sensors are based on modern measurement techniques and involve optical,
20 acoustic and radar measuring principles, rather than the more traditional gravimetric (see
21 e.g., Cauteruccio et al. [1]) and seldom adopted thermodynamic ones (see e.g., Cauteruccio
22 et al. [2]).

23 However, the lack of any standardized calibration procedure for non-catching instru-
24 ments (Lanza et al. [3]) and the differences still observed between measurements from co-
25 located modern and traditional (reference) instruments (see e.g., Lanza and Vuerich [4])
26 still make the reliability and accuracy of the new sensors largely questionable. The role of
27 external influencing variables, such as the environmental conditions at the measurement
28 site, is also rarely accounted for, and no adjustments are usually applied to the raw data
29 to correct e.g., for the wind-induced bias (Chinchella [5]). Therefore, their use in applica-
30 tions out of the research framework should not be encouraged before sufficient
31 knowledge of both the instrumental and environmental sources of bias is achieved and
32 suitable adjustments are implemented.

33 The development of opportunistic sensors is the second main innovation recently
34 experienced, suggesting a high potential for large-scale application due to the low cost of
35 their installation and operation. These sensors exploit already-existing, but usually unre-
36 lated, microwave (MW) or millimeter wave (mmW) links to infer the rainfall amount or
37 intensity by interpreting the extra attenuation induced by the precipitation on the received
38 signal level. Communication technologies that can be opportunistically used for rain sens-
39 ing include commercial MW links (CMLs) of cellular phone networks, satellite MW links
40 (SMLs), including broadcast satellite links (BSLs), but also wireless sensor networks
41 (WSNs), e.g., for Internet of things (IoT) applications, moving vehicles, surveillance cam-
42 eras, etc. (see e.g., Uijlenhoet et al. [6], Giannetti et al. [7], Haberlandt and Sester [8] and
43 Allamano et al. [9]). These sensors turn out appropriate for large-scale installation (e.g.,
44 within citizen scientist initiatives) and coverage of wide areas, where in-situ rainfall meas-
45 urements are rarely sufficient or even possible. However, the availability of comprehen-
46 sive and convincing validation exercises is still scarce (see e.g., Colli et al. [10]) and as-
47 sessing their accuracy is difficult. Indeed, opportunistic sensors in most cases provide cu-

48 mulative information about rainfall along some geometric path (from linear to unpredict-
49 able), which does not match the coverage of any traditional instrument that could be used
50 as a reference.

51 Weather radars and remote sensors on board meteorological satellite platforms have
52 been largely developed and used to measure rainfall over wide areas, with increasingly
53 enhanced spatial and temporal resolution. These are based on various remote imaging
54 systems operating in different bands of the light spectrum (from visible to MW wave-
55 lengths). Their main advantage is the spatial coverage of wide geographical areas, with
56 the capability to provide areal averaged estimates of the rainfall field over hydrological
57 units (the catchment area) where many applications operate (e.g., flood forecasting, water
58 resources management, etc.). However, the associated rainfall products largely rely on in-
59 situ rainfall measurements for calibration and validation purposes. Following Michael-
60 ides et al. [11] “measurements at the ground have been proved indispensable, despite ad-
61 vances in several areas of remotely sensing of precipitation”.

62 To provide specific guidance about instrument calibration and their achievable accu-
63 racy, perform laboratory and field tests, and develop research/technical activities about
64 the measurement of precipitation intensity and the related data analysis and interpreta-
65 tion, the first Measurement Lead Centre on Precipitation Intensity was designated by the
66 World Meteorological Organization (WMO) in Italy in 2010 [12]. The Lead Centre is ded-
67 icated to the memory of, and named after, Benedetto Castelli and his historical work on
68 precipitation measurements. A reference system for rainfall intensity observations is
69 available at the field test site of the Lead Centre in Vigna di Valle (Rome, Italy) for testing
70 the performance of various existing and new rain sensors. Installed in a pit, it is composed
71 of a set of working reference instruments employing a selection of measuring principles
72 tested during the previous WMO Field Intercomparisons of Rainfall Intensity Gauges (see
73 Lanza and Vuerich [4]).

74 2. Overview of Contributions

75 This Special Issue (SI) collects papers about rain sensor technologies and applica-
76 tions, with the goal of providing the readership with an understanding of operating prin-
77 ciples, state-of-the-art, applications, and future trends of such devices. Contributions were
78 provided by researchers from both academia and industry on many different aspects of
79 rain sensor technologies and applications, spanning over different measuring principles,
80 measurement scales, and the measured characteristics of the rainfall process (intensity,
81 drop size distribution, fall velocity, etc.). Papers touch upon on the various aspects of sen-
82 sor calibration, uncertainty assessment, standardization, and validation.

83 This SI includes seventeen contributions: two of them are in the form of surveys,
84 while the remaining fifteen are feature papers presenting the state-of-the-art of the tech-
85 nology, applications, case studies, prototypes, results of measurement campaigns, and in-
86 novative solutions for rain sensing. The devices and technologies addressed are:

- 87 • catching rain gauges;
- 88 • non-catching rain gauges (disdrometers; laser precipitation monitors; piezoelectric
89 sensors);
- 90 • weather radars and spaceborne remote sensing platforms;
- 91 • opportunistic rain sensing (CML, SML/BSL, IoT);
- 92 • gamma-dose rate monitoring;

93 Authors affiliations are from nineteen countries across all continents (Africa, North
94 and South America, Asia, Europe and Oceania) and the papers present experimental re-
95 sults obtained in seven countries (China, Italy, Kenya, Mexico, Poland, Puerto Rico-USA,
96 and Spain).

3. Contributions

3.1. Rain gauges

An empirical assessment of the impact of wind on accumulated precipitation measurements in Poland is presented by Barańczuk et al. [13], who analyzed daily precipitation data obtained from two catching type instruments, the Hellman totalizer rain gauge and the GGI 3000 evaporimeter set (with collector areas varying from 200 to 3000 cm², respectively). The cylindrical, Hellman gauge is positioned on a pole at 1.0 m above the ground while the evaporimeter, still cylindrical in shape, is positioned at 0.05 m above the ground. Though the height range is limited, a significant difference of 3–4 % was observed in the collected precipitation at the yearly scale, which the authors attribute entirely to the aerodynamic impact of wind on the sensor.

Stagnaro et al. [14] performed dynamic calibration in the laboratory on two catching type drop counter instruments and applied the developed adjustment curve to real-world measurements from a field test site at the Hong-Kong Observatory. The rainfall climatology at the site was found to be crucial in determining the magnitude of the measurement bias, with a predominant overestimation at the low to intermediate rainfall intensity range. This work demonstrates the relevance of the instrumental sources of bias even for sensors adopting quite simple technologies (optical in this case), and the need for accurate calibration before operational use.

The accuracy and calibration issues of non-catching instruments for in-situ rainfall measurements are addressed in a couple of papers. Baire et al. [15] focus on quantifying the instrumental bias and present a traceable method for their calibration, using high precision rain drop generators. Three different European institutes, National Standards (Belgium), Danish Technological institute (Denmark) and the University of Genova (Italy) developed their own version of the calibration device and presented an estimate of the associated calibration uncertainty. The work is propaedeutic to the development of standardized procedures, which are presently under discussion within the European Standardization Body (CEN), Technical Committee 318 (Hydrometry).

On the other hand, Chinchella et al. [16] investigated the environmental bias due to the influence of wind on rainfall measurements obtained from the Thies LPM instrument, a laser disdrometer providing measurements of both raindrop size and fall velocity. Results suggest a strong impact of wind on the measurement accuracy, depending on the wind speed and direction, since the gauge body is not radially symmetric and cannot be easily aligned with the prevailing wind at the site.

In the paper by Antonini et al. [17], the development of a prototype of an impact rain gauge based on a very low-cost piezoelectric sensor was presented. Machine learning methods were tested and compared for the calibration of the relationship between the different properties of the voltage signal, as sampled by the rain drop impact, and rainfall intensity. Although some potential is evident, additional validation is still needed, especially in different seasons and on different types of precipitation.

3.2. Weather radars & spaceborne platforms

A statistical cross-evaluation study of the radar reflectivity from the dual-frequency precipitation radar (DPR) onboard the Global Precipitation Measurement Mission (GPM) and the U.S. National Weather Service (NWS) Next-Generation Radar (NEXRAD) ground-based instrument was performed by Acosta-Coll et al. [18] over the island of Puerto Rico (USA). The GPM at Ku-band and Ka-band and NEXRAD at S-band overlapping scanning regions were compared during typical weather precipitation events and during four extreme weather events. The authors found that the correlation coefficient between the two instruments during the analyzed extreme weather events (including tropical cyclones) was moderate to low, depending on the elevation angle of the ground-based radar.

148 A method for rain area detection and correction from reflectance and infrared (IR)
149 brightness temperatures data of the Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) satellite are pre-
150 sented by Kingsley et al. [19]. A gradient based adaptive correction technique was devel-
151 oped to reduce the number and size of the detected rain areas. After calibration and vali-
152 dation with rainfall data from a dense network of ground-based rain gauge stations in
153 South-Western Kenya, the model showed good agreement in the spatial dynamics of the
154 detected rain area and rain rate.

155 3.3. Opportunistic sensing techniques

156 Due to rainfall's high spatial and temporal dynamics, accurate real-time monitoring
157 of rain intensity and retrieval of the rain map are very challenging tasks. To this respect,
158 rain gauges, weather radars, and satellite remote sensing, i.e., the three main rainfall meas-
159 urement methods at present, exhibit some limitations and drawbacks. In the last few dec-
160 ades, the use of pre-existing MW (or mmW) communication links (i.e., dedicated to other
161 communication services), as sensing signals gained increasing attention and emerged as
162 a very promising technique capable of providing rainfall estimates with high spatial and
163 temporal resolution. The basic idea for this approach to rain sensing, termed opportunist-
164 ic, relies on: i) measuring the extra attenuation of the signal caused by the presence of
165 precipitation along some MW (or mmW) propagation path, and ii) mapping this attenua-
166 tion into a rain rate value, via signal processing based on some tropospheric model, e.g.,
167 the popular power law relationship between the rainfall rate (in mm/h) and the rain-in-
168 duced attenuation (in dB).

169 The paper by Lian et al. [20] contains a comprehensive survey on rainfall estimation
170 based on opportunistic measurement of the extra attenuation introduced by the rain on
171 CMLs, such as the fronthaul/backhaul communications among base stations of mobile
172 networks. The paper introduces the basic principle of this technique, reviewing the state
173 of the art solutions for the different steps of signal processing, also addressing uncertain-
174 ties and errors involved in each step, as well as their impacts on the accuracy of rainfall
175 measurement. Challenges and future directions are eventually discussed.

176 Nebuloni et al. [21] assess the performance of a network of CMLs as opportunistic
177 rainfall sensors in a challenging mountainous environment in Northern Italy. The bench-
178 mark dataset was provided by a set of rain gauges and disdrometers. Data gathered from
179 disdrometers were first used to calibrate the power law relationship, then CML-based
180 rainfall estimates were derived and compared with rainfall sensor measurements. Exper-
181 imental results show that CML opportunistic technique is effective in rainfall detection,
182 whereas its quantitative rainfall estimates may exhibit large discrepancies.

183 Song et al. [22] used eight MW links (operating at 15 GHz and 23 GHz) for real-time
184 rain rate estimation in Jiangyin (Eastern China). A strong positive between the rain-in-
185 duced attenuation of MW links and the rain rate measured by rain gauges was demon-
186 strated. Furthermore, real-time results indicate that MW links estimate the rainfall with a
187 higher temporal resolution than customary rain gauges.

188 The paper by Zheng et al. [23] introduces a field experiment using a 3 km long link
189 in the E-band (71–81 GHz) of the mmW range to obtain rainfall rate information in Nan-
190 jing city (Eastern China). The implemented algorithm first distinguishes between the wet
191 and the dry periods, then determines the classification threshold for calculating attenua-
192 tion baseline in real time, corrects the influence of the wet antenna attenuation and finally
193 calculates the rainfall rate through the power law relationship between the rainfall rate
194 and the rain-induced attenuation. Experimental results, expressed in terms of correlation
195 and relative error between the rainfall rate retrieved from the mmW link and that meas-
196 ured by a raindrop spectrometer, demonstrate the reliability and accuracy of the proposed
197 rainfall monitoring technique.

198 A different approach to opportunistic rain sensing is based on the measurement of
199 the attenuation induced by rain on SMLs, either BSLs for direct-to-home TV reception
200 from geostationary (GEO) satellites in Ku (10–13 GHz) and Ka (17–20 GHz) bands, or

201 signals from low-Earth orbit (LEO) satellites belonging to large constellations for global
202 broadband access.

203 Giannetti and Reggiannini [24] present a broad overview of the numerous issues in-
204 herent in the SML-based rain monitoring approach, along with a number of solutions and
205 algorithms proposed in the literature in recent years, and ultimately provide an exhaus-
206 tive account of the current state of the art on this topic.

207 Pastoriza-Santos et al. [25] experimentally outline some of the characteristics and
208 drawbacks affecting the propagation of a radio beacon in Ka-band from a GEO satellite to
209 a ground-based measurement equipment, made of low-cost commercial-grade devices, as
210 in case of SML-based opportunistic rain sensing. The paper describes a procedure for eval-
211 uating and subtracting the baseline level corresponding to no-rain conditions from the
212 raw received beacon signal. The impact of some meteorological parameters and the una-
213 voidable (though small) antenna pointing errors are presented, too.

214 In the paper by Shen et al. [26], dual-polarized MW signals from LEO satellites are
215 employed for raindrop size distribution retrieval. The feasibility of this approach is stud-
216 ied by modelling and simulating the retrieval system, including multiple ground receivers
217 equipped with signal-to-noise ratio estimators and a LEO satellite communicating with
218 the receivers using both vertically and horizontally polarized signals. Simulation results
219 confirm that the specific attenuation ratio of vertically to horizontally polarized signals
220 can be effectively used to retrieve the slope and intercept parameters of raindrop size dis-
221 tribution.

222 Saggese et al. [27] propose a novel algorithm to estimate the rainfall rate map from
223 attenuation measurements on both BSLs and CMLs. The approach pursued therein ex-
224 tends the well-known two-dimensional GMZ (Goldshtein-Messer-Zinevich) algorithm to
225 fuse the attenuation data coming from different links in a three-dimensional scenario.
226 Simulation results prove the convergence of the procedures and show that adding the BSL
227 links to a pre-existent CML network boosts the accuracy performance of the estimated
228 rainfall map.

229 Another opportunistic technique for rain sensing consists in the measurement of the
230 attenuation induced by rain on WSNs. To this respect, Gutiérrez-Gómez et al. [28] devel-
231 oped a novel sounding system based on the measurement of point-to-point long range
232 (LoRa) chirp radio signals in the 915 MHz industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) band.
233 The system was tested in a case study close to and over water in a tropical meadow region,
234 the Colima River in Mexico. The results show that the LoRa signal propagation over water
235 exhibits a log-normal distribution. Furthermore, two new experimental path loss models
236 are presented.

237 3.4. Non-conventional techniques

238 Yakovleva et al. [29] used measurements of γ -radiation dose rate ambient equivalent
239 performed with a scintillation detector BDKG-03 (at 1 minute sampling rate) to confirm
240 that a change in the intensity of precipitation leads to a change in the γ -radiation dose rate
241 increase speed (time derivative). The authors propose a method of estimating the average
242 value of the intensity and amount of precipitation for one event, reconstructing the inten-
243 sity spectrum from experimental data on the dynamics of the measured dose rate of γ -
244 radiation. Reconstruction of various events and comparison with ground based measure-
245 ments using a Davis Rain Collector II and an optical (laser) precipitation gauge, named
246 OPTIOS, show the good performance of the proposed method.

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